

Fig. 1. Structure of trimer complex $(S_4N_4H_4.ZrOCl_2)_3$.

with the calculated ones for various groups confirms the presence of free S-N,N coordinated S-N and N-H bands^v as indicated by the ir spectra. The axial ratios and axial angles computed as $a_0 = b_0 = 12.18 \text{ \AA}$, $c_0 = 24.36 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$ and $\gamma = 120^\circ$, express the hexagonal geometrical structure of the complex (Fig. 1). The repeating of peaks and subsequently blurring of the spectra confirm the presence of various groups and trimer form of the complex.

TABLE 1—X-RAY POWDER DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF COMPLEX

2θ	(hkl)	d (Obs.) Å	d (Calcd.) Å	I/I_0
7.2	100	12.97	12.18	13.33
7.4	100	12.86	12.18	8.33
12.5	111	7.02	7.02	6.66
22.0	221	4.04	4.05	10.00
23.3	310	3.83	3.85	13.33
25.0	222	3.56	3.51	11.66
26.0	320	3.43	3.37	8.33
27.7	321	3.22	3.25	10.00
32.7	331	2.74	2.79	20.00
38.3	333	2.35	2.34	83.33
41.3	440	2.18	2.15	8.33
44.5	442	2.03	2.03	100.00
53.6	551	1.70	1.70	1.66
58.4	553	1.58	1.58	3.33

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Preparation and Characterisation of some 3d Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxymaleianilic Acid and 2-Carboxymaleianilic Acid

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In this paper we report the preparation and characterisation of some 3d metal complexes of 2-hydroxymaleianilic and 2-carboxymaleianilic acids.

Experimental

2-Hydroxymaleianilic acid (OH-Ma) and 2-carboxymaleianilic acid (OC-Ma) were prepared^{1,2} by the condensation of maleic anhydride and *ortho*-substituted-aromatic amines.

All the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

To an ethanolic solution (250 ml) of 0.02 M OH-Ma and OC-Ma, 0.25 M KOH was added with stirring until pH of the solution reached ≈ 8 . To it 0.02 M aqueous solution (250 ml) of the metal salts were mixed with stirring and digested over a water-bath for 1 h. The crystalline precipitates so obtained were filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallised. Chlorides of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , acetate of Cu^{II} and freshly prepared hydroxide of Cr^{III} were used for preparing the complexes.

Results of elemental analysis, molar conductance data of the complexes in dimethylformamide and magnetic moment values at 26° are stated in the

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		N	Metal		
Complexes of OH—Ma					
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₇ N)Cr	Dull green	4.36 (4.51)	16.61 (16.76)	3.73	13.2
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₇ N)Mn	Dark brown	4.27 (4.46)	17.67 (17.49)	5.98	24.6
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₆ NCl)Fe ^a	Brownish black	4.43 (4.21)	16.58 (16.80)	5.81	15.2
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₇ N)Co	Dark brown	4.26 (4.40)	18.81 (18.52)	4.88	30.4
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₇ N)Ni	Dark green	4.17 (4.40)	18.63 (18.46)	3.02	16.3
(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₇ N)Cu	Dark green	4.47 (4.34)	19.44 (19.69)	1.74	13.5
Complexes of OC—Ma					
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₆ N)Cr	Green	4.42 (4.14)	15.60 (15.37)	3.77	14.1
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₆ N)Mn	Brown	4.27 (4.09)	16.43 (16.06)	6.01	20.8
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₇ NCl)Fe ^b	Orange	3.62 (3.88)	15.71 (15.49)	5.79	24.9
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₆ N)Co	Bluish green	3.89 (4.04)	16.81 (17.03)	4.90	28.6
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₆ N)Ni	Bluish green	3.91 (4.05)	16.72 (16.97)	3.00	15.0
(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₆ N)Cu	Dark green	3.77 (3.99)	18.45 (18.12)	1.77	14.8

*% of Cl = ^a10.38/(10.66), ^b9.67/(9.83).

Table 1. Infrared spectra (KBr) were also recorded. Conductometric titrations and pH measurements were made in aqueous ethanolic medium at 26° and pH observations were corrected for mixed solvents according to Van Uitert and Hass³.

Results and Discussion

pH-metric and conductometric measurements indicated the biprotonic nature of the OH—Ma and OC—Ma. Formation of non-ionic 1 : 1 metal—ligand complexes is proved by conductance measurements, electrometric studies and chemical analysis. Magnetic measurements of the complexes reveal normal spin-only values (Table 1). The complexes were stable on heating upto 180° and did not confirm lattice water.

The medium ir band (3 560 cm⁻¹) due to the OH stretchings of phenol of OH—Ma disappeared in the metal chelates, suggesting the coordination of phenolic oxygen through the metal ion. A strong band at 3 400 and 3 360 cm⁻¹ was assigned for ν_{N-H} in the free OH—Ma and OC—Ma, respectively. This vibration probably merged with the broad band (at 3 280—3 520 cm⁻¹) of OH of the attached water molecule⁴, presence of which was further supported by the appearance of a weak band at 3 655—3 680 cm⁻¹ which has been assigned to antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching modes. Involvement of nitrogen atom in bonding with the metals was proved⁵ here also by the appearance of three bands of varying intensities of amide group in the regions

1 590—1 630, 1 495—1 550 and 1 250—1 280 cm⁻¹ in metal chelates while these stretching bands occurred in the higher region at 1 660, 1 560 and 1 290 cm⁻¹ in free OH—Ma and 1 650, 1 565 and 1 365 cm⁻¹ in free OC—Ma. Moreover, shifting of $\nu_{C=O}$ in free secondary amide from 1 700 cm⁻¹ to the lower frequency region 1 660—1 680 cm⁻¹ may be due to mass effect of the heavy metal ion linked to the nitrogen atom⁶ and thus weakened the C=O linkage rather than the coordination of metal through oxygen⁷.

The sharp ir band occurring at 1 460 and 1 465 cm⁻¹ in OH—Ma and OC—Ma has been assigned due to the combination of C—O stretching and OH deformation of the COOH group, and this band lowered in the region 1 400—1 440 cm⁻¹ with decrease intensity in the ir spectra of metal chelates, suggesting the involvement of carboxylic group in chelation. The sharp band at 980 cm⁻¹ in free ligands was assigned for C—OH. This band disappeared in the metal chelates, which provided strong evidence for the coordination of carboxylate oxygen with the metal. Furthermore, shift of the band occurring at 1 420 cm⁻¹ and 1 415 cm⁻¹ in free OH—Ma and OC—Ma, respectively, due to the carboxylate ion to the lower wavelength region (1 365—1 385 cm⁻¹) confirmed the coordination of metal through carboxylate ion. Similar findings were reported by Sharma *et al.*⁸. The bands due to M—N and M—O were difficult to assign due to their weak absorption intensities.

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Studies on Oxadiazole. Part-VIII. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(2-substituted-benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone

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In view of various biological activities¹ 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, their derivatives of type 1 were prepared by condensing dapsone with monochloromethyl acetate in presence of dimethylformamide. The ester so formed was converted to the corresponding hydrazide by treatment of hydrazine hydrate. The constitution of the product was supported by ir and nmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

1
R = Aryl

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer using DMSO-D₆.

p,p'-Bis(carbomethoxymethylamino)diphenylsulphone : *p,p'*-Diaminodiphenylsulphone (0.01 mol)

in dimethylformamide (30 ml) was added to methyl chloroacetate (0.02 ml) and contents were refluxed for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from dimethylformamide, (90%), m.p. 155° (Found : C, 55.02 ; H, 5.07 ; N, 7.10. C₁₈H₂₀O₆N₂S calcd. for : C, 55.10 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 7.14%).

p,p'-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-(carbomethoxymethylamino)diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol), ethanol (95%) and hydrazine hydrate (100%, 0.02 mol) was refluxed for 36 h. Ethanol was then removed and the product was isolated and crystallised from dimethylformamide, (83%), m.p. 98° (Found : C, 48.88 ; H, 5.08 ; N, 21.37. C₁₈H₂₀O₄N₆S calcd. for : (C, 48.97 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 21.42%).

p,p'-Bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol), methanol (30 ml) and cyanogen bromide (0.02 mol) was refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (67%), m.p. 132° (Found : C, 48.82 ; H, 4.04 ; N, 24.30. C₁₈H₁₈O₄N₈S calcd. for : C, 48.86 ; H, 4.07 ; N, 25.33%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350, (N-H str.), 1 620 (NH def.), 1 395 (S=O asym. str.), 1 180 (S=O sym. str.), 1 685 (C=N str.) and 1 140 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C str.).

p,p'-Bis(2-benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone : A mixture of benzoic acid (0.01 mol), thionyl chloride (0.01 mol) in dioxan (40 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess thionyl chloride was removed by distillation. The product obtained was then refluxed with *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone in dioxan (20 ml) with 2-3 drops of pyridine for further 2 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (75%), m.p. 180° (Found : C, 59.01 ; H, 3.98 ; N, 21.10. C₃₂H₂₆O₆N₈S calcd. for : C, 59.07 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 17.23%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (NH str.), 1 690 (amide-I), 1 510 (amide-II), 1 290 (amide-III), 1 620 (C=N str.), 1 080 (C-O-C str.), 1 340 (S=O asym. str.) and 1 140 cm⁻¹ (S=O sym. str.) ; δ 7.88 (m, ArH) and 2.45 (s, CH₂).

Similarly other aromatic acid chlorides were condensed with *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone. Physical data of the products are recorded in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity : 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles (1) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method². The testing was carried